

EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF FACULTY IN-SERVICE TRAINING: AN INPUT TO COLLEGE LEARNING ACTION CELL

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Extent of Implementation of Faculty In-Service Training: An Input to College Learning Action Cell

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the implementation of faculty in service training of collegiate department of the Tomas Claudio Colleges during the academic year 2023-2024. There were ninety-six (96) who responded in the survey. They were described in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service and position title. Findings reveal that age, civil status, educational attainment are not significant on the respondents' perception regarding the extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program. On the contrary, sex, length of service and position title are found significant. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the results indicate that factors such as age, marital status, and level of education do not have a meaningful impact on how participants perceive the level of implementation of the In-Service Training (INSET) Program. Conversely, gender, years of service, and job title are shown to be influential. Further, the research findings show that factors like age, marital status, and educational background do not play a significant role in how participants view the implementation of the In-Service Training (INSET) Program. However, gender, tenure, and job position are revealed to have a notable impact. The recommendations offered included seminars and trainings and their area of specialization may be continuously provided to teachers to enhance their teaching performance; teachers may be motivated to pursue graduate education through giving of necessary compensation and incentives; scholarship grants may be provided to teachers for their continuous attendance in graduate education program; the proposed training program may be implemented; parallel studies may be conducted considering other variables.

Keywords: *faculty, In-Service training, LAC Session*

Introduction

Education is one of the essential factors needed by human being. Through this, one is being nurtured, honed, skilled, and equipped with the knowledge that will make an individual a contributory factor in the development of nation. In doing so, teacher plays a significant role in shaping the community. Being a facilitator of learning, teachers need to be fully equipped with the theories and technical know-how on how to realize the learning process.

Teachers need to continue upgrading themselves in order to become highly competent and competitive in the field of academe. The kind of practices and performances that they are utilizing has a great effect on the teaching learning process.

The process of LAC sessions involves inquiry and answers that deepens the professional interest of teachers. In line with this, it also connotes self-introspection of what knowledge has transpired, assessment and evaluation and collective competence. Likewise, it embraces the ideals which aim to put forward the teaching and learning process which leads to better learning outcomes of the students. It also connotes flourishing the profession of teachers. It encourages collaborative effort of other professionals towards the advancement of content and pedagogical knowledge, practice, skills, and attitudes. Hence, it cultivates a win-win relationship between the school and the community where stakeholders reside.

The changes made in the educational system through the implementation of K to 12 curriculum faced teachers' dilemmas on finding ways on how to administer the needed competencies of the learners. In addition to the kind of learners so called millennial where simple method may no longer be applicable needs teachers to enhance themselves professionally. They need to continuously grow to deliver quality output to their learners.

The institutional leadership of Tomas Claudio Colleges also recognizes that the quality of learning is influenced by the quality of teaching and its outcomes. Thus, the researchers explored the extent of implementation of in-service training which aims to deeper the level of understanding of teacher on the assessed personal and professional needs based on the result of the conducted Faculty Performance Review during the school year 2022 to 2023.

The researchers would like also to assists the school administrator in providing the real status of the current professional program activities of the collegiate Department towards its continuous service improvement. Moreover, with this study the researchers were able to develop a training program for an effective implementation.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the implementation of faculty in service training of the collegiate department of the Tomas Claudio Colleges during the academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;

- 1.2. sex;
- 1.3. civil status;
- 1.4. educational attainment;
- 1.5. length of service; and
- 1.6. position title?
2. What is the extent of implementation of in-service training with respect to:
 - 2.1. program information and objectives;
 - 2.2. speakership;
 - 2.3. session facilities and services;
 - 2.4. session management; and
 - 2.5. session evaluation?
3. Is there a significant difference between the extents of implementation of in-service training as perceived by the respondents with respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?
4. What are the perceptions of the respondents regarding the implementation of in-service training with respect to:
 - 4.1. personal development; and
 - 4.2. professional development?
5. Is there a significant difference between the extent of implementation of in-service training and the perceptions of the respondents regarding the implementation of in-service training?

Literature Review

Hammond et al. (2017) discussed that teacher professional learning is of increasing interest as a critical way to support the increasingly complex skills students need to learn in order to succeed in the 21st century. Sophisticated forms of teaching are needed to develop student competencies such as deep mastery of challenging content, critical thinking, complex problem solving, effective communication and collaboration, and self-direction.

According to Schwartz (2023), teacher professional development is lauded by some as one of the best ways to improve teaching and learning, scorned by others as a complete waste of time. It's something that teachers might have access to weekly, or barely get once or twice a year. Professional development will be part of almost every teacher's career. They will take district-provided training, participate in collaborative learning groups, or seek out seminars and conferences. When professional development is done well, it provides an opportunity for teachers to grow their knowledge and sharpen their skills, which can lead to better student outcomes.

In addition, Osamwonyi (2016) discussed that the need for in-service education of teachers cannot be underestimated. It is a necessity in enhancing work performance and motivation of teachers in the field. Absence of in-service training of teachers will retard professional growth of teachers as well as "missing gaps" between demands and actual achievement levels. In-service education allows for such activities that may include seminars, workshops, conferences, classes, and exhibitions etc. that are designed to develop and improve employees in an organization from the initial employment stage to retirement.

Likewise, Culajara (2023) posited that the implementation of the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) enhances the teaching and learning process to achieve the addressed goals in the curriculum. These goals address equality and quality services in education, thus this can be implemented when the instructional leaders and teachers have the grit in improving their competencies through professional development. One of the key components of helping teachers become more effective is professional development (PD). Through this action, more efficient and adaptable to the evolving educational context can be attained and learning progresses in line with the enormous transformations brought by industrialization and globalization.

Relatively, Villaneza et al. (2018) explained that the Learning Action Cells (LACs) is DepEd's primary mechanism for the professional development of teachers it is defined as a group of teachers who engage in collaborative learning sessions to solve shared challenges encountered in the school facilitated by the school head or a designated LAC leader (DepEd Order 26, 2016). Essentially, LAC's are purposeful, school based and cost efficient professional development activities which aim to continuously improve teachers pedagogical skills, instructional strategies, and assessment practices, which in turn, will result in students improved academic achievement.

Moreso, Silva (2018) states that pursuant to section 15 of Article IV of Republic Act 1032 known as Continuing Professional Development Act, the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) and Philippine Regulatory Boards (PRB) hereby adopt and promulgate the implementing rules and guidelines to carry out the provisions of 10912. It is hereby promulgated that the State shall institute measures that will continuously improve the competence of professionals in line with the national standards of practice, thereby ensuring their contribution in uplifting the general welfare, economic growth and development of the nation.

Meanwhile, the study of Serapion (2018) examined the role of in-service teachers training on improving teaching and learning process in public secondary schools in BMC. Generally, the study findings show that, proper INSET does improve the teaching and learning process which in turn improves students' performance. That means when INSET programs are introduced through best strategies like, doing research to determine the needs, selecting teachers/participants as per best established criteria, being as inclusive as possible by

involving many participants, using up to date and relevant teaching and learning materials, establishing appropriate intervals between one cohort and using competent trainers, among others, bring positive results.

As capsulized in the study of Gumban and Pelones (2021), teacher quality can develop holistic learners who are value-driven, qualified with 21st century skills, and capable of driving the country toward the development and progress. The study aimed to find out how the activities of School Based Learning Action Cell (SLAC) as a lesson study program in the Philippines relates to Teacher's Work Performance. Based on simple linear regression, the data showed that when teachers participate in SLAC activities, their work performance increases. Implications for the professional development of teachers are given in the study.

Furthermore, the study of Gumban (2019) aimed to find out the School-Based Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Activities has relationship on work performance of teachers in Norala Districts. Findings revealed that the extent participation of elementary teachers in the School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Activities was implemented to a highly described. The level of work performance of the elementary teachers in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy described as very satisfactory level of assessment; while learning environment and diversity of learners described as very satisfactory; moreover for curriculum and planning described as very satisfactory; likewise assessment and reporting described as very satisfactory; furthermore plus factor is an ordinal logistic regression because it is a single ordinal variable while the first four models are simple linear regression which treated as continuous variables.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive method of research specifically the descriptive survey research design utilizing the research-made questionnaire checklist to gather the needed data. Zulueta (2020) asserted that descriptive research is concerned with conditions and relationships that exists, practices that prevail, beliefs and process that are going on, effects or trends that are being developed. In addition, descriptive research describes the data and characteristics about the population or phenomena being studied. The principal aim in employing this method is to describe the nature of situations as it exists at the same time explore the causes of a particular phenomenon. Likewise, it determines the nature of prevailing conditions with practice and seeks description of activities.

Respondents

The study considered the total population of the faculty members of the collegiate department of Tomas Claudio Colleges. This consist of ninety-six faculty members. They were described in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, length of service and position title.

Instrument

The study utilized the researcher-made questionnaire checklist as the primary instrument in order to get the needed data.

It has three parts. The first part dealt on the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, and educational attainment, length of service and position title. Part II showed the level of implementation of the faculty's in-service training in terms of program information and objectives, speakership, session facilities and services, session management and session evaluation. Last part dealt on the perceptions of the respondents regarding the implementation of in-service training with respect to personal development and professional development. Each aspect is composed of 5 items with a total of 35 items.

Procedure

The study was conducted in the following manner. Initially, a five-point researchers' made questionnaire was prepared and validated by three (3) College Professors who are expert in the field of research. Then, permission was asked from the Office of the President. When permitted, the questionnaire checklist was disseminated through Google form. The questionnaire checklists were retrieved. The retrieved questionnaires were collated, recorded, analyzed and interpreted.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables

As reflected in the table, out of 96 teacher-respondents, 30 or 31.3 percent have ages 49 years old and above while 24 or 25 percent belongs to age bracket 42-48 years old. Meanwhile, 16 or 16.7 percent have ages 35-41 years old, and the remaining percentage have ages 21-38 years old. There are more females than males with 61 or 63.5 percent out of 96 teachers. In terms of civil status, most of them are married with 58 or 60.4 percent.

In terms of educational attainment, majority of them are with post-graduate degrees, 32 or 33.3 percent of them are with Ph.D. or Ed. D units and 31 or 32.3 percent are with Masteral Degree. About their length of service, 39 or 40.6 percent have been in the service for 6-10 years and 7 or 7.3 percent are 26-30 years. As regard to their position title, 34 or 35.4 percent are Instructor, 23 or 24 percent are Assistant Professor, and the rest are Associate Professor and Professor.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
49 years and above	30	31.3	1
42-48	24	25.0	2
35-41	16	16.7	3
28-38	13	13.5	3.5
21-27	13	13.5	3.5
Total	96	100.0	
<i>Sex</i>			
Male	35	36.5	2
Female	61	63.5	1
Total	96	100.0	
<i>Civil Status</i>			
Single	32	33.3	2
Married	58	60.4	1
Widow/Widower	6	6.3	3
Total	96	100.0	
<i>Educational Attainment</i>			
Doctorate Degree	20	20.8	3
With Ph. D. or Ed. D. Units	32	33.3	1
Masteral Degree	31	32.3	2
With MAED or MAT Units	11	11.5	4
Undergraduate Degree	2	2.1	5
Total	96	100.0	
<i>Length of Service</i>			
26-30 years	7	7.3	5
21-25 years	21	21.9	2
16-20 years	13	13.5	4
11-15 years	16	16.7	3
6-10 years	39	40.6	1
Total	96	100.0	
<i>Position Title</i>			
Professor	20	20.8	3
Associate Professor	19	19.8	4
Assistant Professor	23	24.0	2
Instructor	34	35.4	1
Total	96	100.0	

Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Program Information and Objectives, Speakership, Session Facilities and Services, Session Management, and Session Evaluation

Table 2. *Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Program Information and Objectives*

<i>Program Information and Objectives</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	The committee set well- defined objectives in the conduct of activities.	4.72	Always	5
2.	It follows the SMART principles.	4.73	Always	4
3.	It is aligned in the vision mission statement of the College.	4.77	Always	2
4.	The objectives are aligned in the activities.	4.75	Always	3
5.	It provides sense of direction towards the end of the activities.	4.78	Always	1
Overall WX		4.75	Always	

As reflected in the table, with respect to program information and objectives, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.75 interpreted Always. Findings indicate that program information and objectives is always implemented in LAC trainings. This means that LAC trainings focus on continuous learning for teachers, promoting the enhancement of their expertise in various aspects of education conforming to the objectives of the school.

This implies that the in-service training program conducted in schools is a well-designed and well-thought-out program with a string foundation for success.

This relates with the statement of Gamboa (2023), that LAC sessions provides wider opportunity to level-up and guide teachers in promoting their knowledge, attitude and competencies for the effective and efficient implementation and delivery of curriculum, instruction and assessment in all schools, conforming to the aim of LAC in developing and supporting “successful teachers by fostering their knowledge, attitudes, and competencies”, as they perform and execute quality delivery of curriculum, instruction, and assessment

in the classroom setting.

Table 3. *Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Speakership*

<i>Speakership</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Everyone is encouraged to become a resource speaker.	4.49	Often	4
2.	Re-echoing is being held every time a teacher attended a seminar.	4.40	Often	5
3.	Time allotment is given to the resource speaker.	4.82	Always	1
4.	Incentives in a form of stipend are given to the speakers.	4.78	Always	2
5.	Recognition is reflected in the faculty performance evaluation tool.	4.70	Always	3
Overall WX		4.64	Always	

As depicted in the table, with respect to speakership, three (3) items are interpreted Always with an overall weighted mean of 4.64. Findings reveal that as perceived by the respondents, the speakership is always implemented in the conduct of the LAC session. This means assigned time for the resource speaker is enough to tackle his topic as well as sharing of lessons learned were always implemented.

This is in connection with the citation of Binauhan (2021) that implementers of LAC session performed their role as resource person and there is a very great extent of manifestation of 21st century skills among teachers and share current trends and practices on curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment.

Table 4. *Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Session Facilities and Services*

<i>Session Facilities and Services</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	The venue suits to the number of participants.	4.86	Always	1
2.	The venue has provision for complete facilities.	4.74	Always	4
3.	The venue is comfortable.	4.78	Always	3
4.	Training materials are provided.	4.63	Always	5
5.	Food allocation is given to the participants.	4.80	Always	2
Overall WX		4.76	Always	

It could be gleaned from the table that with respect to session facilities and services, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.76 interpreted Always. Results denote that logistics, and comfort is always a priority of the institution in the conduct of the in-service training programs. This means that comfortable and well-equipped facilities with necessary resources create an environment conducive to focused learning and collaboration, providing adequate facilities and services demonstrates respect for the participants' time and investment in their professional development.

This implies the venue accommodates the number of participants comfortably, avoiding overcrowding or cramped conditions and the program provides food for participants, which can be helpful for maintaining energy and focus throughout the session.

This relates with the statements of Gamboa (2023) that the school principal or a chosen leader within the Learning Action Cell (LAC) endeavors to cultivate a supportive, empathetic, and secure environment within the school-based communities of practice or structured Professional Learning Communities (PLC).

Table 5. *Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Session Management*

<i>Session Management</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Communication correspondence is properly disseminated.	4.71	Always	2
2.	Record keeping is being observed in assuring that all participants are being informed.	4.63	Always	4
3.	Formulation of program committee is being practiced in the conduct of program.	4.64	Always	3
4.	Committee is well distributed.	4.56	Always	5
5.	Key persons of every committee follow and perform the task at hand.	4.75	Always	1
Overall WX		4.66	Always	

As depicted in the table, with respect to session management, as perceived by respondents, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.66 interpreted Always. Results indicate that as observed by respondents, the session management is always implemented in the LAC session. Findings implies that the delegation to make the best use of teachers their time and skills as well as ensuring that staff and subordinates are assisted in their growth and development,

This is in connection with the ideas of Osamwonyi (2016) that teachers who are highly involved in SLAC activities their work performance increases. In-service education is designed for the manpower development of the school system and the educational enterprise. If teachers are to perform their functions effectively and efficiently, it becomes imperative for them to require training in new skills and modern methodology.

Table 6. Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training Programs with Respect to Session Evaluation

Session Evaluation		WX	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1.	Evaluation tool is given at the end of the program.	4.86	Always	1
2.	Evaluation tool achieves objectivity.	4.77	Always	4
3.	Evaluation tool welcomes constructive criticisms.	4.78	Always	2.5
4.	Evaluation tool calls for improvement.	4.75	Always	5
5.	The result of the evaluation is being utilized in research.	4.78	Always	2.5
Overall WX		4.79	Always	

As depicted in the table, with respect to session evaluation, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.79 interpreted Always. Results reveal that session evaluation is always implemented during the conduct of in-service training to assess whether these programs are able to achieve its intended outcome, and if the training materials and resources used are aligned with or meet the school objectives. Findings implies that evaluation identifies training or session gaps, discover opportunities for improving session, provide feedback which would be used as basis for improving practices to ensure that it is delivered effectively and efficiently. This is in connection with the study of Mendoza, et al. (2017), his paper discusses the transferability of Lesson Study vis-à-vis Learning Action Cell in a university setting.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

The table depicts that with respect to the different aspects, in terms of age, civil status, educational attainment, the probability values are all greater than .05. This fails to reject the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program with respect to the different aspects in terms of the cited variables. On the other hand, in terms of sex, length of service and position title, the null hypothesis is rejected having probability values less than 0.5.

Findings reveal that age, civil status, educational attainment are not significant on the respondents’ perception regarding the extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program. On the contrary, sex, length of service and position title are found significant. This implies that that sex, length of service and position title have bearing on how the respondents’ view the implementation of In-service program in TCC.

Table 7. Result of the F-test on the Significant Difference on the Extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to the Cited Aspects in Terms of Their Profile

Aspect	F-value	p-value	Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Age				
Program Information and Objectives	0.059	0.993	Accepted	Not Significant
Speakership	1.383	0.246	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Facilities and Services	0.969	0.428	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Management	1.229	0.304	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Evaluation	0.817	0.517	Accepted	Not Significant
Sex				
Program Information and Objectives	9.852	0.002	Rejected	Significant
Speakership	4.586	0.035	Rejected	Significant
Session Facilities and Services	3.726	0.057	Rejected	Significant
Session Management	9.442	0.003	Rejected	Significant
Session Evaluation	18.084	0.000	Rejected	Significant
Civil Status				
Program Information and Objectives	2.807	0.066	Accepted	Not Significant
Speakership	1.114	0.333	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Facilities and Services	0.574	0.565	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Management	1.566	0.214	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Evaluation	1.246	0.292	Accepted	Not Significant
Educational Attainment				
Program Information and Objectives	1.215	0.310	Accepted	Not Significant
Speakership	2.073	0.091	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Facilities and Services	1.448	0.225	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Management	2.131	0.083	Accepted	Not Significant
Session Evaluation	1.968	0.106	Accepted	Not Significant
Length of Service				
Program Information and Objectives	3.143	0.018	Rejected	Significant
Speakership	2.636	0.039	Rejected	Significant
Session Facilities and Services	3.201	0.017	Rejected	Significant
Session Management	2.487	0.049	Rejected	Significant

Session Evaluation	2.464	0.050	Rejected	Significant
Position Title				
Program Information and Objectives	5.478	0.002	Rejected	Significant
Speakership	5.926	0.001	Rejected	Significant
Session Facilities and Services	6.632	0.000	Rejected	Significant
Session Management	11.044	0.000	Rejected	Significant
Session Evaluation	13.541	0.000	Rejected	Significant

This related to the study of Madriaga (2021) that teachers have different perceptions in the implementation of the SLAC because of their different age bracket, gender, and experience in the field of teaching, position, and educational attainment.

Program enhancement is still needed for the improvement of SLAC Implementation among Elementary Schools and conduct SLAC sessions regularly based on the needs of the teachers.

Perceptions of the Respondents Regarding the Implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program with Respect to Their Personal Development and Professional Development

Table 8. *Perceptions of the Respondents Regarding the Implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program with Respect to Their Personal Development*

<i>Personal Development</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	I gain newer insights every time I attend CLAC sessions.	4.84	Always	1
2.	It enhances myself and improves my self-confidence.	4.76	Always	4
3.	I got first-hand experience with effective communication, goal setting and life coaching.	4.71	Always	5
4.	I gain inspiration from the speakers and peers.	4.82	Always	2
5.	I enjoy attending to the session because it improves me as a person and manages to connect to other people.	4.78	Always	3
Overall WX		4.78	Always	

It could be gleaned from the table that with respect to personal development, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.78 interpreted Always. Results denote that in-service training program enhance teachers’ knowledge after attending due to exposure to new ideas, perspectives and best practices, broadening their understanding and expertise. This means the program promotes personal growth by leading to improved well-being and stronger connections with others.

This implies that in-set programs contribute to teachers’ personal development in various ways, boosts teachers’ self-confidence, leading to a stronger sense of self-worth and professional identity.

This is contradictory to the result of the study of Alfaidi and Elhassan (2020) which concluded that most of in-service training programs do not contribute to the personal and cultural needs of the teacher development and these teachers claimed that most of teacher training programs that they have attended did not discuss the teachers personal or educational needs.

Table 9. *Perceptions of the Respondents Regarding the Implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program with Respect to Their Professional Development*

<i>Professional Development</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Attending to sessions enables me to gain mores expertise in my field.	4.77	Always	4
2.	I develop new ideas and techniques that can be incorporated in my teaching style.	4.81	Always	2
3.	It enhances my productivity, flexibility and versatility.	4.72	Always	5
4.	It keeps me updated and relevant on the changing trends and directions in the field of academe.	4.79	Always	3
5.	It transforms me into a better and more apt educator by enabling me to create relevant and tailored course instructions for today’s students.	4.82	Always	1
Overall WX		4.78	Always	

It could be gleaned from the table that with respect to professional development, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.78 interpreted Always. Results denote that the in-service training make teachers enhance their skills enabling them to adopt to different situations and learning styles. In addition, it equips the educators with the skills to create relevant and tailored course instruction for today’s students.

This implies that a successful in-service program depends on the quality and relevance of the offered session and provide opportunities for teachers to share their own experiences and learn from each other.

This relates with the statements of Hammond et al (2017) effective professional development (PD) is needed to help teachers learn and refine the instructional strategies required to teach these skills that focuses on teaching strategies associated with specific curriculum. Professional development supports teachers’ learning focusing on teaching strategies classroom contexts.

Significant Difference on the Extent of Implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to the Personal and Professional Development in Terms of Their Profile

Table 10. Result of the F-test on the Significant Difference on the Extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program as Perceived by the Respondents with Respect to the Personal and Professional Development in Terms of Their Profile

Aspect	F-value	p-value	Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Age				
Personal Development	1.106	0.358	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	1.800	0.136	Accepted	Not Significant
Sex				
Personal Development	5.514	0.021	Rejected	Significant
Professional Development	7.411	0.008	Rejected	Significant
Civil Status				
Personal Development	1.635	0.201	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	3.485	0.035	Accepted	Not Significant
Educational Attainment				
Personal Development	1.353	0.256	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	1.305	0.274	Accepted	Not Significant
Length of Service				
Personal Development	2.789	0.031	Rejected	Significant
Professional Development	3.485	0.011	Rejected	Significant
Position Title				
Personal Development	2.465	0.067	Accepted	Not Significant
Professional Development	7.128	0.000	Rejected	Significant

The table depicts that with respect to the different aspects, in terms of age, civil status, educational attainment, the probability values are all greater than .05. This fails to reject the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents on the extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program with respect to the personal and professional development in terms of the cited variables. On the other hand, in terms of sex, length of service and position title, the null hypothesis is rejected having probability values less than 0.5.

Findings reveal that age, civil status, educational attainment are not significant on the respondents' perception regarding the extent of implementation of In-Service Training (INSET) Program. On the contrary, sex, length of service and position title are found significant.

This implies that that sex, length of service and position title differs on how the respondents' view the implementation of In-service program in. This further implies that teachers with longer service may have different perspectives compared to those who are relatively new to the profession. Teachers in leadership positions, may place greater emphasis on leadership training and development opportunities compared to classroom teachers.

This related to the study of Lumanao (2018), he concluded that personal characteristics of the teachers have no bearing on their professional development. He recommended that administrators may keep on planning and implementing professional development programs for the teachers for them to enhance their competencies and attain more quality learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The results indicate that factors such as age, marital status, and level of education do not have a meaningful impact on how participants perceive the level of implementation of the In-Service Training (INSET) Program. Conversely, gender, years of service, and job title are shown to be influential.

The research findings show that factors like age, marital status, and educational background do not play a significant role in how participants view the implementation of the In-Service Training (INSET) Program. However, gender, tenure, and job position are revealed to have a notable impact.

In the light of the findings, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

Seminars and trainings and their area of specialization may be continuously provided to teachers to enhance their teaching performance.

Teachers may be motivated to pursue graduate education through giving of necessary compensation and incentives.

Scholarship grants may be provided to teachers for their continuous attendance in graduate education program.

The proposed training program may be implemented.

Parallel studies may be conducted considering other variables.

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